

“SHARQ TARONALARI” - INTERNATIONAL MUSIC FESTIVAL IN SAMARKAND

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Abstract: The article shows that the international music festival is a powerful factor in the spiritual health of the Eastern world, including the musical values of the Uzbek people, in order to set their development on the right track.

Key words: status, song, big song, epic, art, music, ud, qabuz, festival

Uzbek classical music has a rich and incomparable heritage. It is extremely ancient and has gone through many centuries of historical processes, and it is significant because it has not lost its value today. "Uzbek people's speech, art, crafts, and architecture are as old as their music is.

Mahmud Kashgari, a famous historian and linguist of the 11th century, mentions a lot of musical instruments (sounds) in his work "Devonu lug'otit turk". He especially emphasizes that oud and koboz sozi are widespread. The scientist also notes that the performance of songs and maqams improved and developed during this period. In fact, traditional music samples of various genres and forms created by our ancestors have become an integral part of our artistic and spiritual heritage. In particular, the old and always popular singing, big singing, epic and status arts of Uzbek classical music have developed and progressed in various forms over the centuries¹.

¹ M.Achildiyeva 2021 Academic Yunus Rajabi and His Scientific Heristage Annals of Romanian Society for Cell Biology 25(4) 9092-9100

It is not for nothing that hafiz, musicians and singers who rely on the strains of our national music have won a deep place in the hearts of the people and gained world reputation with their unique performance methods. Uzbek music is a powerful tool for understanding the national spirit and qualities of the people, and for cultivating nobility, greatness, and beauty in a person. A living encyclopedia of the people's musical heritage." ²

Under the leadership of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, great work was done to restore and develop the rich history, rich cultural heritage, and national values of the Uzbek people.

"Indeed, with the honor of great independence, a number of exemplary works have been carried out aimed at the preservation and further development of old and artistically perfect music samples in the country.

The decisions of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on November 17, 2017 "On measures to further develop the art of Uzbek national status" and "On holding the international status art conference" on April 6, 2018 were important documents that started a new era in the history of Uzbek classical music.

Musical competitions held in the republic and regions "Boysun Bahori", "Zulfiya" and "Nihol" state awards and international music festivals "Sharq Taronalari" of great global importance are a clear example of this. ³

Among these festivals, "Sharq taronalari" with its great potential, unique image, life charm, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Sharq taronalari" international music festival is traditionally held every two years in the last week of August in the city of Samarkand. Transfer is scheduled. The city of Samarkand, included in the UNESCO World Heritage List, can be called the "Jewel of the East".

² Shashmaqom traditions and modernity. Proceedings of the international scientific conference. T.2005y page 5.

³ Sh. Oikhojayeva "Maqom taronalari" Vol. 2011, page 5.

The International Music Festival "Sharq Taronalari" is held in Registan Square, one of the unique architectural structures of the city of Samarkand, which has been known as the "Gate of the East" for several years, and has surprised the peoples of the world with its historical monuments and greatness, classical music and plays a major role in spreading the art of Uzbek national music to the world.⁴

Major musicologists, well-known scientists and public figures, art connoisseurs, meticulous specialists from different countries of the world took part in it and witnessed a real art festival.

"This festival is held in cooperation with UNESCO, the leader of the United Nations organization in the fields of education and science, culture and art.

In addition, the fact that classical music is giving way to show business in the world today increases the need for a musical conference that unites the original spiritual values of different nations in the form of classical music."⁵ The main purpose of the festival is to spread the achievements in the art of classical music to the general public, to support talented and talented young people who are studying music and singing, to connect international creative relations, and based on the promotion of the ideas of friendship and tolerance.

⁴ Magazine of the IX "Sharq Taronalari" international music festival. Samarkand 2013// Uzbekistan page 4

⁵ www.Sharq taronalari.uz internet network

This international music festival shows that the musical values of the Eastern world, including the Uzbek people, are a powerful factor in improving the spiritual health of today's life, and putting the development on the right track. Uzbek youth who are hungry for knowledge should answer with all their strength and knowledge in spreading the art of Uzbek national classical music to the whole world and preserving it.

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